

Stop Playing: African Writers and the Abandonment of Oral Tradition

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Emerencia Nwapa

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African intellectuals and writers often celebrate the richness of oral tradition, but when it comes to actually capitalising on it, they gravitate toward the *novel* — a Western literary form. The 1980s, with the popularity of radio cassettes, was supposed to be the golden age for African oral storytelling. But the chance was sadly missed.

Therefore, this is what has been happening: **celebrating one form while abandoning it in practice.**

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I scratch my Zulu knots and ask myself:

- Is it really about preservation of tradition, or about acceptance into global literary circles?
- Why didn't more African artists lean into radio, spoken word, or cassette storytelling during that era?
- Was the written novel seen as more "serious" or prestigious?
- Is there a lingering colonial mindset around what counts as "literature"?

Hypocrisy? Maybe. Or maybe a sign of how deeply colonial structures have shaped what is seen as legitimate culture.

African Literature

Chinua Achebe

Unmodified Adoption

Linguistic Assimilation

Oral Tradition

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Written by Emerencia Nwapa

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I love books, am lucky to work in a college library in the middle of Africa. I am a mother of two. I write about education, books, and culture.

Responses (3)

Write a response

What are your thoughts?

Will Brubacher
Apr 23

The overarching question for any writer, anywhere, is finding ways of getting their voice/story out in the world, and I don't think, it's an easy challenge for anyone. Writers have always had to compete within their own culture and in the larger... [more](#)

16

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Vinanti Sarkar ... VoicesofWomenWorldwide
Apr 30

Hello Emerencia ... Lovely to read your informative write up on **African intellectuals and writers celebrating the richness of oral tradition ... when it comes to actually capitalizing on it**, Sorry to **learn they gravitate toward the novel — a Western...** [more](#)

1 reply

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Roderick Balenda he/him
Apr 18

I think a lingering colonial mindset played a role in what counted as literature, back in the day, because during deeper colonial periods, there were many African writers whose work and storytelling weren't acknowledged, due to the way they were... [more](#)

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